

LEAST MASTERED COMPETENCIES IN BRITISH-AMERICAN LITERATURE: BASIS FOR AN EVALUATION OF DIGITIZED INTERVENTION MATERIAL

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Least Mastered Competencies in British-American Literature: Basis for an Evaluation of Digitized Intervention Material

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Abstract

This study aimed to develop and evaluate digitized intervention material in British-American Literature for Grade 9 students at Rizal High School in Pasig City during the academic year 2022-2023. The respondents of the study were the fifteen (15) English Teachers and fifteen (15) English Experts of Rizal High School. The descriptive method of research was used with a survey questionnaire as data gathering instrument. Based on the findings, the English experts and English teacher-respondents evaluated the developed digitized intervention material in British-American Literature for English 9 as Very Satisfactory (VS) in terms of Content Quality, Instructional Quality, and Technical Quality. Likewise, there is no significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents on the developed digitized intervention material. Moreso, the readability level of the material indicated that the reading texts are suitable for the ninth grade. Comments and suggestions were provided by the respondents to further improve the digitized reading material.

Keywords: *reading material, digitized, literature*

Introduction

Teaching nowadays requires several techniques and appropriate pedagogies that would make the learning process authentic, meaningful, and relevant to the lives of the learners. Not all students are motivated by the same values, needs, desires and wants. Some students are motivated by the approval of others or by overcoming challenges.

Relatively, innovations in the educational system have emerged to provide solutions to the problems and needs of the learners in boosting the value of their learning (Bangayan-Manera, 2019). Approaches like differentiated group activities, collaborative learning, technology-based instruction, and peer learning, among others, have been demonstrated to be essential methods for enhancing the performance of students.

Significantly, instructional materials play a vital role in helping the learners grasp the competencies that they need to understand. These materials enhance students' skills, capabilities, knowledge, and confidence in sharing the lessons that they have learned. Learners are surrounded with so many distractions. Some of them can adapt easily, while others need more time and instructions to understand a certain concept.

In addition, intervention materials are greatly considered tools for remediating the low achievements of the learners even before the emergence of the K-12 Basic Education Program. Consequently, Strategic Intervention Material or SIM was proposed for the methods of teaching to encourage the interest of the students and thereby improve their level of understanding. It is strategically constructed and planned for teaching remediation for low achievers in the subject and given after a regular classroom teaching to students who were not able to comprehend the concepts of a subject matter.

Cubillas (2018) noted that Strategic Intervention Materials in English are considered rare. The use of sufficient and strategically designed instructional materials suited for every type of learner is greatly encouraged, especially in teaching English. In language learning, instructional materials are viewed as the essential source of comfort and self-esteem for English language teachers. There's an ease to share knowledge to the learners if instructional materials are accessible for them to utilize. This is primarily the basis for why the availability of instructional materials is fundamental in classroom teaching.

Due to innovations and advancement of technology, Pinar (2021) has realized that the use of technology-based instructions, can give students a more remarkable opportunity to learn a specific competency. It can also empower the idea of the relationship of learning in terms of collaboration, participation, engagement, and in-depth learning attainment.

This study is based on technological and pedagogical content knowledge. (TPACK) - Educational Framework. The importance of combining education with technology is apparent. Incorporating technology into teaching practices can enhance dynamic and student-centered classroom interactions. TPACK consists of three parts. These include content knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, and technological knowledge.

Research Questions

This study attempted to develop and evaluate Digitized Intervention Materials in British-American Literature in Rizal High School during the School Year 2023-2024. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the top six least mastered learning competencies in British-American Literature based on the first three quarterly

assessments during School Year 2022 - 2023?

2. What is the evaluation of the English teachers and English experts on the developed Digitized Intervention Material in terms of the following criteria:
 - 2.1. content quality;
 - 2.2. instructional quality; and
 - 2.3. technical quality?
3. Is there a significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents on the developed digitized intervention material in British-American Literature in terms of Content Quality, Instructional Quality and Technical Quality?
4. What is the readability level of the reading texts included in the developed digitized intervention material based on the Automated Readability Index (ARI) readability formula?
5. What are the comments and suggestions offered by the two groups of respondents to improve the developed digitized intervention material?

Literature Review

According to Bandola (2019), English is a common language that is vital for obtaining different competencies in learning. These competencies are indispensable part and necessary to boost, advance, and discover in everyday activity. It is a must for the educators to give the learners a variety of learning materials that will encourage them to enhance their English language skills and gain full confidence in the mentioned field.

Aysu (2020) mentioned that educators can enhance language acquisition by tailoring it to students' ages, interests, and abilities. To address this issue, they can use flexible materials, diverse skill sets, and engaging classroom instructions.

To encourage and support these low achiever learners, the Department of Education (DepEd) presented the utilization of Strategic Intervention Materials (SIM) as a form of remediation to improve their academic performance in schools. DepEd Memorandum No. 117 s. 2005, "Strategic Intervention Materials (SIM) Training Workshop for Successful Learning," opened the opportunity for teachers to develop and utilize SIM in classrooms. Different needs of the learners are enumerated by strategies and interventions.

Cubillas (2018) defined Strategic Intervention Materials as teaching materials created for remediation purposes that are contemplated as one of the solutions utilized by DepEd to escalate the academic success of learners showing low progress in class.

When it comes to innovation and technological advancement, Taguiam (2021) said that innovation in teaching is characterized when teachers utilize interactive teaching methods and digital content materials to stimulate student's love in learning. When the relevant strategies and skills are implemented with the use of technology, making it beneficial tool for teaching, then greater teaching effectiveness can be established.

To productively use the digitized intervention material and attain the intended objectives, teachers must observe its parts meaningfully (Galang, 2018). Based on the DepEd SIM format, these are the essential parts of the digitized intervention material are: guide card, activity card, assessment card, enrichment card and reference card.

The study of Camba (2023) entitled "Digitized Remedial Instructional Materials in Afro-Asian Literature for Grade 8 Learners" sought to develop and evaluate digitized remedial instructional material in Afro-Asian Literature for Grade 8 learners. Camba's study revealed that the respondents evaluated the developed Digitized Remedial Instructional Materials in Afro-Asian Literature for Grade 8 Learners as Very Acceptable in terms of Content Quality, Instructional Quality, and Technical Quality.

Furthermore, Aranda et.al (2019) emphasized that SIM is a teaching-learning tool designed for the sake of both teachers and students. Its aims are to stir up pupils' interest; absorb theories and abilities; and put into actions the absorbed theories and abilities into actual situations. Arpilleda (2021), added that the given tasks, ideas and competencies must constantly intertwined to obtain the expected outcome. It should be verified prior to utilizing it in the class and it should be convenient to reproduce.

Methodology

Research Design

The descriptive type is the method used in this study. According to Singh (2023), the goal of descriptive research is to portray the features of a phenomenon or subject that is being studied through a methodological approach. It demands observing and collecting data on a specific topic without trying to infer cause-and-effect relationships. The aim of descriptive research is to give broad and precise picture of the population or phenomenon being studied and to describe the relationships, patterns, and trends that exist within the data.

Respondents

The sources of data are the 15 English Teachers and 15 English Experts from Rizal High School which were analyzed to evaluate the Digitized Intervention Material in British-American Literature.

Instrument

The instrument utilized in the study was the survey questionnaire. The questionnaire was used to extract the evaluation of the 15 English experts and 15 English teachers on the developed Digitized Intervention Material in British-American Literature.

The survey questionnaire used by the researcher was adapted from Evaluation Rating Sheet for Non-Print Materials by LRMS Assessment and Evaluation with some modifications with the help of her evaluators and adviser. The questionnaire dealt with the development and evaluation of the E-SIM in English 9 with respect to the following criteria: Content Quality, Instructional Quality and Technical Quality.

Procedure

Permission to conduct the research study was first secured by the School Division Superintendent of Pasig City and the School Principal of Rizal High School. After having sought their permission, the researcher used the least mastered skills in English 9 record for S.Y. 2022-2023, of the Grade 9 which is the basis in developing the materials. The parts in designing the digitized intervention material are Guide Card, Activity Card, Assessment Card, Enrichment Card and Reference Card.

The researcher personally administered the survey questionnaire to the teacher-respondents for the evaluation of the Digitized Intervention Material in British-American Literature. She personally retrieved them to ensure completion of the required respondents.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

Top Six Least Mastered Learning Competencies in British-American Literature Based on the First Three Quarterly Assessment During School Year 2022 – 2023

Table 1. *Computed Mean and Rank of Least Mastered Competencies on the First Three Quarterly Assessment During School Year 2022 – 2023*

Quarter	Competencies	Incorrectly Answered	Percentage	Rank
1	Express permission, obligation, and prohibition using modals	1101	55.62	4
1	Use conditionals in expressing arguments	882	44.27	7
1	Employ the appropriate communicative styles for various situations (intimate, casual, conversational, consultative, frozen)	1377	69.13	3
2	Make connections between texts to particular social issues, concerns, or dispositions in real life	1450	72.50	2
2	Analyze literature as a means of understanding unchanging values in the VUCA (volatile, uncertain, complex, ambiguous) world	1516	75.80	1
3	Differentiate biases from prejudices	979	47.80	6
3	Determine the relevance and the truthfulness of the ideas presented in the material viewed	999	51.13	5
3	Judge the validity of the evidence listened to	758	41.83	8

The facts presented in Table 2 reveals that the competencies such as “Analyze literature as means of understanding unchanging values in the VUCA (volatile, uncertain, complex, ambiguous) world” acquired the highest average of 75.80 which occupies the first rank, while placing in the second, third, fourth, fifth and sixth ranks are the following competencies: “Make connections between texts to particular social issues, concerns or dispositions in life”, “Employ the appropriate communicative styles for various situations (intimate, casual, conversational, consultative, frozen)”, “Express permission, obligation and prohibition using Modals”, “Determine the relevance and truthfulness of the ideas presented in the material viewed” and “Differentiate biases from prejudices.”

This implies that the six competencies in the first three quarterly assessment were the most difficult topics in British American Literature for the Grade 9 students which could be used to develop digitized intervention material

Evaluation of the English Teachers and English Experts on the Developed Digitized Intervention Material in British-American Literature

Table 2. *Respondents’ Evaluations on the Developed Digitized Intervention Material in British-American Literature as to Content Quality*

	Content Quality		Respondents			
			Teachers		Experts	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Content is consistent with topics/skills found in the DepEd Learning Competencies for the subject and grade/year level it was intended.	4.00	VS	3.93	VS		
2. Concepts developed contribute to enrichment, reinforcement, or mastery of the identified learning objectives.	4.00	VS	3.87	VS		
3. Content is accurate.	4.00	VS	3.73	VS		

4. Content is up-to-date.	4.00	VS	3.87	VS	
5. Content is logically developed and organized.	3.93	VS	3.80	VS	
6. Content is free from cultural, gender, racial, or ethnic bias.	3.80	VS	3.87	VS	
7. Content stimulates and promotes critical thinking.	4.00	VS	3.80	VS	
8. Content is relevant to real-life situations.	4.00	VS	3.87	VS	
9. Language (including vocabulary) is appropriate to the target user level	3.93	VS	3.80	VS	
10. Content promotes positive values that support formative growth	4.00	VS	3.93	VS	
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.97	VS	3.85	VS
	Standard Deviation	0.06		0.30	

It implies that the content quality of the digitized intervention material in British-American Literature is consistent with topics/skills found in the DepEd Learning Competencies for Grade 9. Developed concepts contribute to enrichment, reinforcement, or mastery of the identified learning objectives. Language used is appropriate to the target grade level. Contents are accurate, up-to-date, logically developed and organized, free from cultural, gender, racial, or ethnic bias, stimulates and promotes critical thinking, relevant to real-life situations, and promotes positive values that support formative growth.

Del Castillo (2021) asserts that it is essential for both the contents and skills be easily understood. The topics covered should be in line with the Department of Education's standards, and the content should be presented in a logical and orderly sequence.

Table 3. Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed Digitized Intervention Material in British-American Literature as to Instructional Quality

Instructional Quality	Respondents				
	Teachers		Experts		
	WM	VI	WM	VI	
1. Purpose of the material is well defined.	3.87	VS	3.93	VS	
2. Material achieves its defined purpose.	3.80	VS	3.80	VS	
3. Learning objectives are clearly stated and measurable.	3.93	VS	3.80	VS	
4. Level of difficulty is appropriate for the intended target user.	4.00	VS	3.80	VS	
5. Graphics / colors / sounds are used for appropriate instructional reasons.	3.87	VS	3.80	VS	
6. Material is enjoyable, stimulating, challenging, and engaging.	3.87	VS	3.80	VS	
7. Material effectively stimulates creativity of target user.	3.87	VS	3.80	VS	
8. Feedback on target user's responses is effectively employed.	3.80	VS	3.67	VS	
9. Target user can control the rate and sequence of presentation and review.	3.93	VS	3.80	VS	
10. Instruction is integrated with target user's previous experience.	3.93	VS	3.80	VS	
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.89	VS	3.80	VS
	Standard Deviation	0.17		0.40	

It can be inferred that the instructional quality of the developed digitized intervention material in British-American Literature achieves its defined purpose. The level of difficulty is appropriate for the intended grade level, and it makes the topics enjoyable, stimulating, challenging, and engaging. This supports De Guzman's (2021) study, which found that instructional materials provide students sufficient experience to enable them to learn at a higher level, giving students enough time to reflect and evaluate, encouraging good study habits, providing enjoyment while learning, and boosting their self-confidence.

Table 4. Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed Digitized Intervention Material in British-American Literature as to Technical Quality

Technical Quality	Respondents				
	Teachers		Experts		
	WM	VI	WM	VI	
1. Audio enhances understanding of the concept.	3.67	VS	3.47	S	
2. Speech and narration (correct pacing, intonation, and pronunciation) is clear and can be easily understood.	3.87	VS	3.73	VS	
3. There is complete synchronization of audio with the visuals, if any.	3.67	VS	3.73	VS	
4. Music and sound effects are appropriate and effective for instructional purposes.	3.67	VS	3.60	VS	
5. Screen displays (text) are uncluttered, easy to read, and aesthetically pleasing.	3.80	VS	3.73	VS	
6. Visual presentations (non-text) are clear and easy to interpret.	3.80	VS	3.80	VS	
7. Visuals sustain interest and do not distract user's attention.	3.87	VS	3.60	VS	
8. Visuals provide accurate representation of the concept discussed.	3.87	VS	3.73	VS	
9. The user support materials (if any) are effective.	3.87	VS	3.73	VS	
10. The design allows the target user to navigate freely through the material.	3.93	VS	3.87	VS	
11. The material can easily and independently be used.	3.93	VS	3.87	VS	
12. The material will run using minimum system requirements.	3.87	VS	3.73	VS	
13. The program is free from technical problems.	3.67	VS	3.60	VS	
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.81	VS	3.71	VS
	Standard Deviation	0.33		0.44	

This may also mean that the technical quality of the developed digitized intervention material in British-American Literature provides screen displays (text) and Visual presentations (non-text) which are uncluttered, easy to read and interpret, and aesthetically pleasing. The application used for this digitized intervention material allows the users to navigate it freely and independently. This is comparable to Camba’s (2023) study that a lesson is more pleasurable when the teaching material is formatted appropriately. There is ample space between paragraphs, the font is readable, the images are informative and clear, and the other drawings and pictures are presented in an understandable manner.

Test of Significant Difference Between the Evaluations of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Digitized Intervention Material in British-American Literature

Table 5. *Test of Significant Difference in the Evaluation of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Digitized Intervention Material in British-American Literature as Regards Content Quality*

Respondents	n	OWM	s	Computed t Value	Critical t value	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	15	3.97	0.06	1.51	2.05	Fail to reject the H0	Not Significant
Master Teachers	15	3.85	0.30				

At a 5% significance level, this means that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. Hence, there is no significant difference in the evaluation of the English teachers and English expert respondents on the developed digitized intervention material in British-American Literature with respect to content quality. This implies that the two groups of respondents concur that the content quality of the developed digitized intervention material in British-American Literature contains learning competencies that are logically developed and organized.

Table 6. *Test of Significant Difference in the Evaluation of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Digitized Intervention Material in British-American Literature as Regards Instructional Quality*

Respondents	n	OWM	s	Computed t Value	Critical t value	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	15	3.89	0.17	0.78	2.05	Fail to reject the H0	Not Significant
Master Teachers	15	3.80	0.40				

As exhibited in the table, the computed t value of 0.78 is less than the critical t value of 2.05. Thus, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis at a 5% level of significance. Hence there is no significant difference in the evaluation of the English teachers and English expert respondents on the developed digitized intervention material in British-American Literature with respect to instructional quality. This means that that the two groups of respondents agree that the instructional quality of the developed digitized intervention material in British- American Literature shows suitability of instructions to attain the learning objectives.

Table 7. *Test of Significant Difference in the Evaluation of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Digitized Intervention Material in British-American Literature as Regards Technical Quality*

Respondents	n	OWM	s	Computed t Value	Critical t value	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	15	3.81	0.33	0.68	2.05	Fail to reject the H0	Not Significant
Master Teachers	15	3.71	0.44				

It is apparent in the table that the computed t value of 0.68 is lower than the critical t value of 2.05. This implies that there is insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis, at a 5% significance level. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the evaluation of the English teachers and English expert respondents on the developed digitized intervention material in British-American Literature with respect to technical quality. This concludes that the two groups of respondents agree the technical quality of the developed digitized intervention material in British-American Literature demonstrates visual effectiveness for achieving educational objectives.

Readability Level of the Reading Texts Included in the Developed Digitized Intervention Material Based on ARI Readability Formula

Table 8. *Readability Level of the Reading Texts Included in the Developed Digitized Intervention Material Based on ARI Readability Formula*

Reading Texts	Score	School Level	Age
The Man with the Hoe By Edwin Markham	9.3	9th Grade	14-15
I Think Continually of Those Who were Truly Great By Stephen Spender	9.29	9th Grade	14-15
I Have a dream By Martin Luther King Jr.	9.07	9th Grade	14-15
Does your Family Important to You? (Article)	9.13	9th Grade	14-15
The Great Depression (Article)	9.35	9th Grade	14-15
Romeo and Juliet (Summary)	9.1	9th Grade	14-15

It can be seen in Table 11 that the following texts included in the Developed Digitized Intervention Material are appropriate for the ninth grade, or ages 14 to 15, based on ARI Readability Formula: The Man with the Hoe By Edwin Markham, 9.3; I Think Continually of Those Who were Truly Great By Stephen Spender, 9.29; I Have a dream By Martin Luther King Jr., 9.07; Does your Family Important to You? (Article) 9.13; The Great Depression (Article), 9.35; and Romeo and Juliet (Summary), 9.1.

Comments and Suggestions Offered by the Two Groups of Respondents to Improve the Developed Digitized Intervention Material

The comments and suggestions of the two groups of respondents to improve the developed Digitized Intervention Material for English 9 were as follows:

Comments:

When developing instructional materials for students, meticulous attention to detail and pedagogical efficacy are essential. The design process requires a delicate mix of theoretical frameworks, empirical evidence, and practical insights to guarantee that the products fit the different needs of learners. The two groups of respondents provided the following feedback to help enhance the Developed Digitized Intervention Material.

(a) The material achieved its purpose, well-constructed and easy for the learners to follow/use; (b) The thorough analysis and well-conceptualized activities will truly make and impact to students; (c) Intervention Material is user – friendly and easy to navigate; (d) Instructional material is well-designed and informative; (e) Graphics are relevant to the topic; (f) The content is well-developed and can truly support learners' acquisition of the target skills. Moreover, it fosters critical thinking and creativity; (g) The digitized intervention material appears to be very engaging and is indeed helpful for the further understanding of the lessons; and (h) The material is very interactive and caters to the different levels of learning. The activities are varied and address high - order thinking skills.

Suggestions:

Ensuring that materials are rationally structured and presented in an understandable manner improves students' capacity to acquire complicated topics and retain information. Furthermore, combining a variety of multimedia elements, such as images, interactive simulations, and audio snippets, can cater to students' unique learning preferences, increasing engagement and enhancing understanding. Researchers can create dynamic learning environments favorable to students' academic growth and performance by adopting the suggestions made by the two sets of respondents and continuously revising instructional materials through iterative feedback loops.

(a) Audio and background music can still be improved; (b) Add rubric on the essay; (c) For incorrect responses, offer specific guidance on what was incorrect and why; (d) Include more questions on inferencing, analyzing and synthesizing; (e) Other interactive add-ons were also great addition to the material, purchasing the paid version of Kotobee will be of great improvement to the material and help teachers easily create readily available features.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study the following are the conclusions drawn from the results of the study. Digitized Intervention Materials for Grade 9 Students can be created based on the least-mastered learning competencies in British-American literature. The developed digitized intervention materials are highly acceptable as to content quality, instructional quality, and technical quality. The reading texts included in the developed digitized intervention material are suitable for ninth-grade students based on the Automated Readability Index (ARI) readability formula.

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